

INTEGRATION OF BUSINESS INNOVATIONS IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS: THE PATH TO PROFESSIONAL EXCELLENCE

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Аннотация. В современном образовательном дискурсе вопрос о внедрении бизнес-инноваций в программы подготовки учителей начального образования становится все более актуальным. Данная проблема показывает необходимость формирования эффективной системы обучения на основе бизнес-инноваций в соответствии с требованиями современных профессионально-ориентированных образовательных учреждений. В ходе проведения программно-коррекционного эксперимента автор подчеркивает необходимость внедрения «бизнес инноваций» в учебные курсы для обеспечения качественного образования и подготовки специалистов, адаптированных к современному обществу. Одним из примеров успешной реализации этой идеи является открытие инновационного бизнес-клуба под названием «Smart Coach» в Казахском национальном педагогическом университете имени Абая, Институте педагогики и психологии. Клуб был запущен для создания инновационной среды, в которой студенты развивают предпринимательские навыки и изучают новые методы в образовании. Также, текущие реформы в сфере образования, реализуемые в стране, направлены на создание условий для формирования высокой нравственности, лидерских качеств, подготовки к профессиональному развитию и инновационной деятельности будущих учителей. Эта статья направлена на изучение существующих исследований и научных работ с целью прояснения значимости интеграции бизнес-инноваций в подготовку учителей и их потенциальных последствий для начального образования.

Ключевые слова: начальная школа, бизнес-инновация, профессиональная деятельность, профессиональный специалист, бизнес-клуб, будущий педагог.

Abstract. In modern educational discourse, the issue of introducing business innovations into primary education teacher training programs is becoming increasingly relevant. This problem shows the need to form an effective training system based on business innovations in accordance with the requirements of modern professionally oriented educational institutions. During the program-correction experiment, the author emphasizes the need to introduce “business innovation” into training courses to ensure quality education and training of specialists adapted to modern society. One example of the successful implementation of this idea is the opening of an innovative business club called “Smart Coach” at the Abay Kazakh National Pedagogical University, Institute of Pedagogy and Psychology. The club was launched to create an innovative environment in which students develop entrepreneurial skills and learn new methods in education. Also, current reforms in the field of education being implemented in the country are aimed at creating conditions for the formation of high morals, leadership qualities, preparation for professional development and innovative activities of future teachers. This article aims to examine existing research and scholarship to clarify the significance of integrating business innovation into teacher education and its potential implications for primary education.

Keywords: primary school, business innovation, professional activity, professional specialist, business club, future teacher.

Introduction. The concept of education in Kazakhstan opens the way to changing the current status of education to a qualitatively different one, different from the previous one. Let's consider one of the possible scenarios for the development of education in the period from 2023 to 2029: from traditional educational programs to preparing students for the future, focusing on updating the value aspect of the content of education, developing global competencies, emotional intelligence, critical thinking, entrepreneurial and financial literacy of students, and differentiation and individualization of learning.[1] Educational programs will continue to be improved to include modules aimed at developing entrepreneurial skills and basic soft skills. Particular attention will be paid to developing the creative and entrepreneurial potential of students. However, there are a number of problems, including the issue of training teaching staff for professional activities with an emphasis on business innovation. Solving these problems requires an integrated approach and active integration of innovations into the education system.

Main part. Increasing entrepreneurial literacy, starting at the primary school level, is an economically rational and relevant, necessary measure. This is because the future of the country's economy is in the hands of professionals. We need specialist teachers who have received special economic training in higher educational institutions and who have sufficient motivation to organize a profession. Professor Isabel Welp from the Technical University of Munich accurately conveyed the importance of entrepreneurship for individuals and society with the following thoughts: “Entrepreneurship is a need of society. This philosophy, based on personal initiative and the understanding that entrepreneurship is not limited to just finding a job, helps a person find his place, builds respect for him and opens the way to true innovation, finding the necessary steps to make the world a better place” [2]. According to scientist Bell Robin, the quality of education in this area can help improve the economic situation of developing countries [3].

Entrepreneurship education can be defined as the development of behavior, attitudes and abilities, and a range of efforts to improve entrepreneurial attitudes, skills and thinking to solve problems such as creativity, innovation, business startup and idea generation. as the pinnacle of entrepreneurial education [4].

Business innovation, characterized by the creation and implementation of new ideas, processes and products, has long been recognized as the driving force behind growth and competitiveness in various industries. In recent years, scholars have increasingly focused on the relevance of the principles of business innovation in the educational field. The parallel between the corporate world and education leads researchers to believe that educators can benefit from adopting innovative approaches to address the changing needs of students and navigate the complexities of today's classrooms. Teaching entrepreneurship was first introduced in the Harvard Business School back in 1945 and has since gained popularity (Mwasalwiba, 2010). It is nowadays widely taught across the globe with special attention in developed countries such as the United States, the United Kingdom, Germany, and the Netherlands. Entrepreneurship courses and programs are offered at universities, high schools, secondary schools, and even at primary schools. This growing interest in entrepreneurship education is due to the fact that the latter has been found to lead to students and young individuals nurturing a lasting interest for entrepreneurship (Torimiro and Dionco-Adetayo, 2005).

The term “entrepreneurship education” is commonly used in the United States and Canada, whereas in the United Kingdom and some parts of Europe, the term “enterprise education” is preferred (Gibb, 1993). This field is very young, emergent, and in its infancy phase (Low, 2001);

it is, hence, natural that it is facing epistemological, theoretical, pedagogical, and practical challenges (Fiet, 2007)

Methods. One important aspect of business innovation relevant to education is **the development of an entrepreneurial mindset** among educators. Scholars such as Draycott and Ray (2011) emphasize the importance of instilling qualities such as creativity, adaptability, and risk-taking in teachers similar to those valued in entrepreneurial ventures. By cultivating an entrepreneurial mindset, educators are better equipped to embrace change, experiment with new teaching methods, and create a culture of innovation in educational institutions. Business innovation refers to innovative methods and strategies applied in a corporate environment to improve efficiency and competitiveness. The application of these innovations in education can bring new approaches to classroom management, individualization of learning and the use of technology in the learning process.

In “The Role of Business Education in Promoting Innovation,” scholars Stephanie Essig and Erica Francis (Essig & Francis, 2016) discuss how business education can promote innovation in a variety of fields, including education. The authors emphasize the importance of implementing innovative teaching methods and collaborating with the business community to ensure effective learning.

Moreover, **the principles of design thinking**, widely used in business to solve complex problems and develop products, promise significant results in improving pedagogical practices. Researchers such as Brown (2008) advocate the application of design thinking methodology in education to enable teachers to empathize with students, identify their needs, and co-create innovative solutions to educational problems. By integrating design thinking into teacher preparation programs, educators can develop a deeper understanding of learner-centered pedagogy and improve their teaching practices accordingly.

Technology integration is another key aspect of business innovation with profound implications for education. As highlighted by Zhao (2018), the rapid development of digital technologies presents both opportunities and challenges for educators. Teacher preparation programs that emphasize technology integration equip educators with the necessary skills to effectively use digital tools, improve teaching effectiveness, and develop students' digital literacy. By using technology-based learning methods, teachers can create dynamic learning environments that accommodate diverse learning styles and prepare students for success in the digital age.

Moreover, the **collaborative nature** of business innovation highlights the importance of networking and partnerships within the education community. Researchers such as Fullan (2016) advocate a collaborative approach to educational innovation in which educators collaborate with peers, industry professionals, and community stakeholders to exchange ideas, share best practices, and co-create innovative solutions. By cultivating a culture of collaboration, teacher preparation programs can foster a sense of collective responsibility among educators and promote a continuous cycle of professional learning and growth.

Implications for primary education. In the context of primary education, integrating business innovation principles into teacher training holds enormous potential for transforming teaching practice and improving student learning outcomes. By equipping elementary school teachers with entrepreneurial thinking, design thinking skills, technological knowledge, and collaboration skills, teacher preparation programs can empower them to create dynamic learning environments that promote creativity, critical thinking, and problem-solving skills among young students.

The literature synthesis highlights a compelling rationale for integrating business innovation principles into teacher education programs, particularly in primary education. By adopting an entrepreneurial mindset, using design thinking methodologies, integrating technology, and fostering collaboration, educators can develop innovative teaching practices that meet the diverse needs of students and prepare them for success in an ever-changing world. Going forward, further research and concerted efforts are needed to examine implementation strategies and the effectiveness of incorporating business innovation into teacher education, with a focus on its impact on primary education pedagogy and student outcomes.

According to these literatures, business innovation in primary schools includes the following aspects:

1. *Entrepreneurial Mindset for Teachers*: Fostering an entrepreneurial mindset among elementary school teachers involves developing creativity, adaptability, and risk-taking. This allows educators to embrace change, experiment with new teaching techniques, and create innovative classroom environments.

2. *Applying Design Thinking Methodology*: Design Thinking provides teachers with tools to understand student needs, empathy, and co-create solutions to educational problems. This helps create learner-centered curricula and improve teaching techniques.

3. *Integrating technology into learning*: The use of modern digital technologies allows teachers to create interactive learning materials that are personalized for each student and provides new opportunities for learning and assessment.

4. *Collaboration and Partnership*: Fostering a collaborative culture among teachers, administrators, parents, and the community encourages the exchange of ideas, the transfer of best practices, and the co-creation of innovative solutions.

Application of these principles in practice includes:

- Organizing trainings and master classes for teachers on the development of entrepreneurial thinking, including methods for encouraging creativity, adaptability and readiness for change.

- Introduction of design thinking methodology into the pedagogical process, through the organization of special courses, workshops and projects that allow teachers to practice empathy, problem definition, and co-creation of solutions.

- Integration of modern technologies into the educational process: Introduction of interactive whiteboards, use of educational applications and online platforms for learning and assessment of progress.

- Creation of educational communities and cooperation networks: Organization of business clubs, regular meetings, forums and seminars where primary education teachers can exchange experiences, share best practices and work together to solve educational problems.

The implementation of these methods in practice will create a stimulating, innovative environment in primary schools, conducive to effective learning and development of students.

Research results. Based on these conclusions and the results of our experiment, we opened a business innovation club “Smart Coach” for students of the educational program “Primary Education with Business Innovation” of Abai KazNPU. The goal of the club is to provide students with the development of business innovative knowledge and skills in the field of professional activity. Club objectives:

- developing in students the ability to think entrepreneurially and see opportunities for realizing their potential;

- developing skills in inventing business ideas and creating a business plan and developing them to the level of entrepreneurial activity;
- development of business modeling skills among future specialists, increasing enthusiasm for private entrepreneurship, training in personal professional growth, development of soft skills, training in self-research.
- formation of research skills and use of modern information technologies.
- development of entrepreneurial skills through participation in master classes of business trainers of the National Chamber of Entrepreneurs of the Republic of Kazakhstan “Atameken”, etc.;

Students' participation in practical classes focused on business innovation allows them to independently determine the criteria for a successful business and gain knowledge that will help them create individual business strategies in modern conditions. In addition, meeting with entrepreneurs and businessmen enriches students' business communication experience and contributes to the development of their organizational and communication skills. Such connections help students expand their network of business contacts and receive practical advice from experienced specialists. Currently, this approach is mainly offered by private universities, which use innovative technologies such as simulation games and VR reality to create students' first business projects [5,6]. Students can choose a company or business project for which they currently work, or submit their own project and develop it under the guidance of a program mentor. If there is no project, the mentor will suggest it. It is very important to have personal guidance from a mentor throughout the learning process[7]. Reviews of the content of entrepreneurship courses have shown that effective teaching methods include case studies, individual presentations, group projects, formal lectures, seminars, guest speakers, online learning and group discussions (Fayolle et al., 2008; Lonappan et al., 2011 ; Solomon, 2008) [8]. All this helps students develop a more complete and practically oriented understanding of business and develop the skills necessary for successful entrepreneurial activity. That is why the formation of qualified specialists is a pressing issue. This is only possible with the formation of an entrepreneurial mindset. It includes the following personal qualities: motivation; active life position, responsibility; creativity; a bunch of; stress tolerance (Sousa & Almeida, 2014) [9]. An innovative club for future primary school teachers can have a positive impact on the professional growth of students. Here are a few reasons why the business innovation club is important for future teachers:

- **Development of Entrepreneurial Skills:** The Business Innovation Club allows students to become familiar with the concepts and principles of entrepreneurship. They can study various aspects of business such as planning, marketing, finance and resource management. Developing these skills will help future teachers be flexible and innovative in their practice and will help them develop their own educational projects or programs.

- **Exchange of experience and knowledge:** Within the club, future teachers have the opportunity to exchange experience, knowledge and ideas with colleagues and experts in the field of business innovation. This allows them to expand their knowledge, learn about best practices and technologies, and receive feedback and constructive advice on their projects and ideas.

- **Networking and Partnerships:** The Business Innovation Club provides aspiring educators with the opportunity to develop valuable professional connections and partnerships. They will be able to meet people from the business sector, representatives of startups, innovative companies and other educational institutions. These connections can open up new opportunities for collaboration, resource sharing, and joint project development.

- **Development of innovative thinking:** The Business Innovation Club promotes the development of innovative thinking of future teachers. They learn to think creatively, find new ways and solutions, and adapt to a rapidly changing educational environment. This helps them better prepare students for the challenges of the modern world and provide quality education that meets the demands of today.

- **Integration of modern technologies and methods:** within the circle, future teachers can get acquainted with modern technologies and methods that help to effectively use innovations in their practice.

The innovative business club Smart Coach prepares future primary school teachers to improve the quality of education, develop creative thinking and readiness for modern challenges in the field of education. It is important to create and implement educational programs that serve as training for future entrepreneurs. Such programs should include not only a theoretical basis, but also practical assignments, projects, cases, work with real business situations and the opportunity to collaborate with enterprises and the business sector. They also promote the development of communication, decision-making, resource management, adaptability and creative thinking skills.

As part of the development of entrepreneurial thinking and practical skills of students of specialty 6B01302 “Primary education with business innovation,” a master class on the topic “Entrepreneurship and Marketing” was organized. A joint event with the innovative business club "Smart Coach" took place on November 20, 2023. The master class brought together leading experts in the field of entrepreneurship and marketing. Students received valuable practical advice and delicacies from the experience of professionals, including information about government grants and the importance of marketing in entrepreneurship.

Discussion. During the event, modern methods of developing competitive specialists, strategies for attracting clients, product placement and creating unique offers on the market were actively discussed. Students showed deep interest in topics related to innovative business, which confirms their potential readiness for entrepreneurial activity. Particular attention is paid to the students’ presentation of their own startup projects. Each project - "Paraqtime", "Ai-Qadam" and "Zholdas" - represents innovative ideas in the field of education and child development. This indicates not only the academic achievements of the students, but also their readiness for entrepreneurial activity. The master class “Entrepreneurship and Marketing” had a positive impact on the students, inspiring them to further develop their ideas and professional skills in the field of entrepreneurship and marketing. Experts assessed the students’ training at a high level, expressing confidence in the successful use of their startup projects in the future. The master class confirmed the importance of an innovative approach in education and entrepreneurship, as well as the relevance of the topic for modern educational programs.

Conclusion. To summarize, it can be argued that the integration of business innovation in education is not only the next step in the development of the educational system, but also a strategic investment in the future of society. It is a collaboration between education and business to create a sustainable and innovative environment that promotes the prosperity of both students and society as a whole.

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